

FRAGMENTATION ANALYSIS OF GLASS FIBRES RECOVERED FROM HYDROLYSIS PROCESSES

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1 Introduction

Composite materials have been extensively used in various industries for past decades with significant successes due to their mechanical strength, design flexibility, reduced weight and low system cost [1], [2]. Based on their benefits, use of composite materials is expected to increase in specific sectors such as transport, where fuel efficiency is a key requirement. An increased use of composites will automatically lead to increased waste, through end-of-life (End-of-Life Directive) and from manufacturing waste. The recovery and reuse of these heterogenous materials is a concern for all industries, industries such as automotive being under considerable pressure to recycle composite materials due to End-of-Life legislation and increased landfill costs. [3] [4].

Majority of composites consist of strong fibre reinforcement (glass or carbon fibres) and thermoplastic or thermoset resins. Various techniques have been reported in the past for recovery of the fibrous reinforcement the most common methods being mechanical granulation and fluidised bed [4] [5].

Mechanical granulation is the most common and cost-effective way to process and recycle composites. Powerful breaking and grinding process are applied which results in a particulate end product that can be used as filler [6]. Despite the low-cost process, the recycle loose its reinforcement properties being too damaged to retain any meaningful performance hence the less desired filler application.

Fluidised bed or in a broader term, incineration, is another well-adopted processing method. The composite can be processed between 500 °C and 1000 °C, either with or without oxygen. Previous results showed that it is possible to retain between 50% and 90% of the fibre original mechanical property although the setup is relatively expensive and the process is known to generate toxic gases in some cases [7] [8].

Hydrolysis processes using subcritical or supercritical water to break down thermoplastic and even stronger thermoset resins has been developed in recent years [7] [9] [11]. As water requires high temperature and high pressure to reach supercritical, once at suitable condition resins can be broken down and dissolved, which results in recycled fibres in an aqueous resin solution [7]. This allows the fibres to be recycled without experiencing significant mechanical force (mechanical granulation) and extreme temperatures (incineration). Although supercritical water can also damage the fibre, various studies pointed out the loss in mechanical property is less comparing to conventional methods. Several recent studies reported fibres processed by hydrolysis could retain approximately 70% to 90% of its original mechanical property [7] [9].

Series of studies at University of Exeter investigated the mechanical properties of recycled glass fibres recovered through different recycling methods for potential use as further composite reinforcement. [7] [10] [11]. This study aims to strengthen the previous research results by investigating the interfacial properties of glass fibres embedded inside thermoset epoxy matrix through fragmentation test

rather than the pull-out test. Single fibre composites consisted of virgin, recovered and silane recoated recovered glass fibres were prepared for fragmentation tests. Critical fragment length and the corresponding fibre strength are obtained in accordance to Weibull model. This enables the calculation of interfacial shear strength (IFSS) and therefore better understanding of fibre mechanical properties for reuse as composite reinforcements.

2 Fragmentation Test

Fragmentation test was first developed by Kelly and Tyson in 1960s and has been widely used for interfacial adhesion analysis between reinforcement and matrix in a composite system [12] [13]. A single fibre composite, or model composite, with a dumb-bell shape has to be prepared and subjected to an axial tension. The purpose of this axial tension is not to break the sample but to induce enough strain so the interface can be effectively disrupted. This normally requires a resin matrix of higher maximum strain than the fibrous reinforcement which results in the fibre breaking into small segments under the axial deformation. Figure 1 shows as the strain gradually gets higher, the embedded fibre breaks into increasingly smaller pieces. However, after a certain level of strain, the fibre fragments stop getting smaller, the fragment becoming too short to transfer enough stress to the fibre, hence no further fibre breakage takes place [13]. At this stage although the sample is not broken there is no requirement to continue the tensile test further as the strain is already at saturation level. Throughout the tension process the fragmentation of embedded fibre is closely monitored by optical microscope and at the end several key data are recorded, namely total amount of fragments and respective lengths.

For interfacial shear strength (τ) calculation a simple force balance approach is used as the following equation shows [14]:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_c(L_c)d}{2L_c} \quad (1)$$

where d is the fibre diameter, L_c is the critical fragment length and σ_c is the fibre strength at the critical fragment length. As a general description, critical fragment length can be considered as the fragment length prior to the strain saturation therefore indicates the minimum length that is effective for stress transfer [15]. A more detailed description in the calculation of critical fragment length can be found elsewhere [15] but in short the critical fragment length (l_c) can be expressed as:

$$L_c = \frac{4}{3} L_{F.avg} \quad (2)$$

where $L_{F.avg}$ is the average fragment length at the end of axial tension. The σ_c is calculated in accordance to a two-parameter Weibull model, which has been widely used in various studies for analysing mechanical properties of brittle fibrous materials such as glass fibres [15] [16]. The model is given by the following equation:

$$P = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{L}{L_0}\left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad (3)$$

where P is the cumulative probability of failure at stress σ when the fibre length is L . σ_0 represents the average fibre strength obtained at gauge length L_0 , whereas Weibull modulus, m , describes the flaw density and can be related to the variation in fibre strength. The higher the m value the less fibre strength variation, suggesting the fibre has better consistency. Equation (3) can then be rearranged to allow calculation of the Weibull modulus, m :

$$\ln\left[\ln\left(\frac{1}{1-P}\right)\right] = m \ln(\sigma) + \left(\ln\frac{L}{L_0} - m \ln \sigma_0\right) \quad (4)$$

It should be noted that the probability of failure for the i^{th} fibre strength, P_i , is decided by following equation [16]:

$$P_i = \frac{i-0.5}{N} \quad (5)$$

where N is the total amount of the sample tested for each type of the glass fibre. After obtaining average fibre strength σ_0 at gauge length L_0 and Weibull modulus (m), critical fibre strength (σ_c) at the critical fragment length (L_c) can be calculated through the equation:

$$\sigma_c(L_c) = \sigma_0(L_0) \left(\frac{L_0}{L_c} \right)^{1/m} \quad (6)$$

which enables the calculation of interfacial shear strength τ in equation (1).

3 Experimental Details

3.1 Glass Fibres and Hydrolysis Process

Glass fibres used for this study were supplied by AHLSTROM in the form a reinforced E-glass fabric. Single glass fibres (virgin fibres) were carefully extracted from the fabric. Samples were cleaned with weak solvent such as isopropanol, rinsed with deionised water and then dried for later use [11]. Same E-glass fabric was also used for composite preparation for subsequent hydrolysis recycling process. Composite panels consisted of unsaturated polyester resin and multi-ply E-glass fabric were prepared and then cut into pieces at proper size for hydrolysis process [7].

The hydrolysis process was carried out by Institut Catholique d'Arts et Métiers (ICAM) with a lab-scale reactor of 500 ml capacity. The reaction is a delicate balance between temperature, pressure, catalyst and time. Detailed description can be found in earlier studies [7] [11]. Composite samples at 40 x 40 mm and distilled water were brought to 300°C for 30 minutes. After the reaction glass fibres (recycled fibres) were dried and collected for subsequent sample testing.

3.2 Silane Preparation and Re-Coating Process

Additional silane coating was applied to the glass fibres collected from the hydrolysis process (recoated fibre). Silquest A-174NT silane coupling

agent supplied by ACC Silicones was used for fibre recoating. The Silquest A-174NT silane is designed to form chemical bonding between fibre surface and resin matrix [7]. Firstly an ethanol-water mixture was prepared in 70:30 ratio. Acetic acid was then added to adjust pH value to 4.5, which is important for the silane activation. Finally the silane was added at 2.5% by weight and the solution was vigorously stirred for at least 2.5 hours before immediate use.

A bundle of recycled fibres was added to the solution for 20 minutes to ensure an even coating. The bundle, now consisting of recoated glass fibres, was then collected and washed with ethanol to remove excessive silane solution. In order to check the presence of silane coating on the recovered glass fibres, 0.1g rhodamine B was added to 100ml ethanol and used as a drop test solution on the bundle of the coated fibres. The presence of red spots on the surface of the coated fibres after immediately washing the fibres with warm water indicates that vinylsilane or methacrylsilane is present and therefore a successful coating [7]. All surface observations were carried out with optical microscope and images captured for later comparison. The recoated glass fibres were dried for 24h prior to any further testing.

3.3 Fibre Morphology (SEM)

All glass fibres (virgin, recycled and recoated) were subjected to SEM imaging for detailed observation on fibre surface morphology. Gold coating was applied to avoid build-up of surface charge and all samples were examined by Hitachi S-3200N scanning electron microscope. Images were saved digitally for further monitoring of fibre diameter variations caused by both hydrolysis and silane recoating processes.

3.4 Single Fibre Mechanical Property Test

Single fibre tensile tests were carried out on all glass fibres based on the method described by ASTM-D-3379-75. Paper frames, as shown in figure 2, were cut for 10 mm gauge lengths and single straight glass fibre was then cut and fixed to the paper frame

using cyanoacrylate adhesive. The sample was then mounted in a single-fibre deformation rig equipped with 10N load cell and precision LDVT driving system, as shown in figure 3.

All samples were carefully examined under optical microscope prior to the test for diameter measurements, as well as for removing samples with clear surface defect or damage. The edges of paper frame were cut off after the sample was fixed to the grips to avoid excessive load to the fibre. All fibres were tested at 2mm/min for a detailed strain-stress recording and minimum of 20 samples were tested for each type of the glass fibres.

3.5 Fragmentation Test

Single fibre composite samples consisting of individual glass fibre and epoxy resin were prepared in accordance to the schematic in figure 4. A silicone mould was used for sample preparation and the chosen matrix was the LY5052 supplied by Mouldlife, UK. This specific epoxy resin system was chosen for its cold-curing features as well as its low viscosity and slow curing rate, which makes it easier to degas and manipulate the composite during its preparation. The resin mixture was first degased in a vacuum chamber for removing air content and then gently poured into the silicone mould until it was half full. Once the resin became semi-cured a single glass fibre was placed at the centre of the gauge length, followed by more resin mixture to fill the mould. The sample was then left to cure at room temperature for 48 hours and then oven cured at 50 °C for 24 hours. Once the composite was fully cured it was carefully removed and polished to the designed dumb-bell shape.

Fragmentation test was carried out on a miniaturised material tester designed and manufactured at Exeter Advanced Technologies (X-AT), University of Exeter, as shown in figure 5. Tensile deformation was applied in steps at 0.25% strain and stopped at 3.0% strain since the purpose is to induce fragments instead of destroy the sample.

The sample composite was closely monitored by stereomicroscope, which allowed the surface strain to be applied incrementally by measuring the distance between the two surface markers. After reaching maximum strain (3.0%) fragments were then measured and counted under optical microscope in order to determine their lengths and the total number of fibre fragments. The findings were then used for interfacial shear strength calculation according to the equations described in section 2.

4 Results

4.1 Glass Fibre Surface Characterisation

Figure 6 shows the SEM images of virgin glass fibres and the recovered glass fibre after hydrolysis process. Although it was reported hydrolysis is a less violent method, a significant fibre diameter reduction can be clearly identified. This is believed to have a direct influence on the fibre mechanical property. The effectiveness of hydrolysis is also demonstrated in figure 6(b). Small pieces of resin residual were found on the surface of recovered fibres, which agrees with earlier studies on the resin removal is likely to be approximately 80% [7].

As explained in section 3.2, recovered glass fibres were then recoated with silane with expectation of improved interfacial bonding. Figure 7(a) shows the SEM image of recoated fibre. It appears the recoated fibre had smooth surface and an increased diameter, which are most likely due to the additional layer of silane coating. To ensure the evenness of silane coating the recoated fibres were exposed to rhodamine B solution and the result can be seen in figure 7(b). Since rhodamine B reacts to the presence of silane, good consistency in colouration and its thickness indicates the silane coating was evenly distributed along the fibre surface.

4.2 Single Fibre Mechanical Property

Results of tensile measurements for all glass fibres can be found in table 1. Previous results by Kao et al [7] are also included since all fibres were obtained

from the same source and treated under same conditions in the hydrolysis process.

The test results of both virgin and recovered glass fibres agreed well with previous findings. The loss in fibre strength was significant and in general agreed with measurements carried out in previous work [7]. As to the recoated fibres, direct comparison was not applicable since previous work used a different silane solutions however certain amount of strength recovery was found in both cases.

4.3 Fragmentation Test

Single fibre composite samples were subjected to axial tension to induce fibre fragmentation. The occurrence and propagation of fragments were observed and recorded via optical microscope. Figure 8(a) shows the typical result of such fragmentation process. Multiple fragments can be easily identified and the software-generated scale allows accurate calculation of actual fragment lengths. Moreover, under a higher magnification, the end of individual fragment can be observed in better detail for the visual evaluation of the effectiveness of interfacial bonding. As seen in figure 8(b), the spike-like feature indicates the bonding was strong enough for the resin to be cracked during the fragmentation.

The amount of fragments and the distribution of the lengths were recorded at the end of the test as shown in figure 9. As a general description it is thought that weak interface tends to have long fragments whereas more but short fragments indicate strong bonding [13] [14] [15].

The rather scattered tail section of recovered fibre is thought to be induced by its inferior mechanical property. Although both virgin and recoated fibres showed similar distribution, recoated fibre appeared to be more concentrated with less scattering. Silane coating is thought to be the cause since the presence of coating increased the diameter and therefore the surface area, which could have had a positive influence on interfacial bonding.

As a qualitative description it appeared that after recoating the recovered glass fibres were able to restore the bonding to the level similar to the virgin glass fibre. For a more detailed comparison interfacial shear strength (IFSS) were calculated so the differences could be quantified.

4.4 Interfacial Shear Strength (IFSS)

As described in section 2, Weibull model was used for the calculation of Weibull modulus, m , and the results can be found in figure 10.

Following equation 6, the critical fibre strength (σ_c) can be obtained based on σ_0 from table 1 and L_c from figure 9. The interfacial shear strength (IFSS) was the calculated according to equation (1). The results can be found in figure 11.

The interfacial shear strength of a bare glass fibre was found at 10.03 MPa, which in general agrees with previous findings [17]. As to the recovered fibre, the IFSS was found to be much lower, 6.12 MPa and most likely due to its inferior tensile strength. Interestingly, the silane recoated fibre was found at 6.89 MPa, which showed 12.6% improvement in terms of interfacial bonding but still much less than the virgin glass fibre. This proves the importance of preserving fibre strength as it was found to be the dominant factor for any significant interfacial adhesion. As to the silane recoating, its presence did improve the bonding although clearly it had a much weaker influence on the matrix-fibre interface. On the other hand, both recovered and recoated fibres reached 60% of the IFSS of virgin glass fibres. Such results suggest that the recovered glass fibre, despite its inferior tensile strength, can improve its adhesion properties and depending on the application be reused.

Conclusions

Results of fragmentation tests and subsequent Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) analysis showed that for recovered glass fibres, the fibre strength was the most important factor regardless of the silane

recoating. Such coating did improve the bonding condition but with only limited effect.

Additionally, single fibre fragmentation tensile tests combined with Weibull model proved to be an effective approach for analysing interfacial adhesion of individual fibres embedded in epoxy resin. It provides a better way than widely used pull-out test, which does not always reflect the actual stress transfer process being more prone to fibre defects during the testing process.

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Fig. 1 Schematic of fragmentation test [13]

Fig. 2 Single fibre sample and paper frame

Fig. 3 Fibre sample and test rig (before cut off)

Fig. 7 Images of silane recoated fibre (a) SEM surface feature, (b) optical with rhodamine B

Fig. 4 Fragmentation test sample

Fig. 5 Fragmentation test setup

	Strength (GPa)	Strain (%)	Diameter (µm)
Virgin	2.08±0.48	2.31±0.81	19.79±0.66
Virgin [7]	2.14±0.51	2.87±0.67	-----
Recovered	1.03±0.25	1.46±0.77	16.54±0.77
Recovered [7]	1.04±0.31	1.41±0.39	-----
Recoated	1.40±0.32	1.52±0.57	18.56±0.59
Recoated *	1.20±0.13	1.66±0.17	-----

* Internal project update report, different silane solution concentration was used

Table 1 Mechanical property of all glass fibres

Fig. 8 Fragmentation images (a) along the fibre and (b) fibre breakage

Fig. 6 Images of (a) virgin, (b) recovered glass fibres

$$L_{c-virgin} = 241.33 \mu\text{m}$$

$$L_{c-recovered} = 366.33 \mu\text{m}$$

$$L_{c-recoated} = 265.67 \mu\text{m}$$

Fig. 9 Distribution of fragment amounts and critical fibre lengths of all fibres

Fig. 11 Calculated interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of all glass fibres

Fig. 10 Two-parameter Weibull analysis for all glass fibres with m values